

New European
Bauhaus

"Digitalising NEB" First Annual Event

digiNEB.eu

SMARTCITY

EXPO WORLD CONGRESS

8 NOV 2023 | BARCELONA & ONLINE

FLIP THE FLYER AND...

"DIGITALISING NEB"

**DIGINEB.EU FIRST ANNUAL
EVENT AT SMART CITIES EXPO
WORLD CONGRESS - SCEWC 2023
7-8 NOVEMBER 2023**

EMBRACING INNOVATION SUSTAINABILITY: DIGINEB AT THE SMART CITIES EXPO WORLD CONGRESS 2023

MERGING DIGITAL INNOVATION WITH URBAN PROGRESS AT SCEWC 2023

The Smart Cities Expo World Congress, held in Barcelona since 2011, has been a beacon of urban innovation, annually gathering global leaders to share insights and advancements in creating smarter, greener, and more efficient urban spaces.

In 2023, this prestigious event provided an ideal backdrop for the first annual "Digitalising NEB" event by digiNEB.eu, a hybrid experience dedicated to exploring the digital transformation of NEB. This convergence was more than just a meeting of minds; it was a powerful synergy of vision and action towards building sustainable and thriving urban futures.

Launched in October 2022, digiNEB.eu is an ambitious initiative aimed at revolutionising the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community. It offers a comprehensive digital platform featuring training courses, a digital toolkit, and an observatory, all designed to foster knowledge sharing, collaboration, and the development of digital solutions within the NEB ecosystem.

SHAPING SUSTAINABLE CITIES

In a world rapidly transforming through digital innovation, the digiNEB.eu project stands at the forefront of this change, particularly in the realm of sustainable urban development

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ENGAGING DISCUSSIONS AND EU COLLABORATIONS

The Smart City Expo World Congress 2023 was a vibrant platform for transformative dialogues. It hosted an array of panel discussions featuring over 30 EU projects, all contributing to the theme of sustainable and smart urban solutions. These sessions, under the banner of "EC Initiatives on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities," highlighted innovative approaches aligned with the EU Green Deal, offering insights into the future of urban living.

The European Commission's booth at SCEWC featured a 120m² space with over 31 partners and 7 EC services. The event hosted 2 Congress and 3 Agora sessions with 30 speakers, along with 15 booth sessions over 3 days featuring 59 speakers. Fifteen delegations were welcomed, representing a diverse range of countries and entities. Attendance was robust, with 40-50 participants at the booth and 60-70 at the sessions. Additionally, 8 networking islands provided partners with dedicated slots for enhanced visibility and collaboration.

URBAN INNOVATION UNLEASHED

A Global Stage for Futuristic Cities and Sustainable Solutions

The Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC) 2023, held from 7 to 9 November, was a landmark event, witnessing over 1,100 exhibitors and 25,300 attendees from more than 800 cities across 140 countries. Featuring 577 speakers across 273 sessions, the congress became a global nexus for discussions on smart and sustainable urban solutions.

The event's focus was on sustainable urban solutions, aligning with the EU Green Deal and the REPowerEU plan. The Smart Cities Marketplace significantly contributed by hosting a 120m² booth, bringing together 31 diverse platforms, initiatives, and projects. It also included engaging sessions with 30 speakers, emphasising the European Commission's initiatives on climate-neutral and smart cities.

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THE SYNERGY OF IDEAS AT SCEWC 2023

Insights on Sustainable Urban
Futures

The Smart City Expo World Congress 2023 was a mosaic of diverse sessions, each contributing to the grand vision of sustainable and innovative urban futures. Among the many enlightening presentations, Mar Muñoz Aparici from TU Delft and part of digiNEB.eu, stood out in her participation.

She spoke at the thematic roundtable titled "Beautiful and Inclusive Transitions to Resilient, Climate-neutral Cities and Communities Driven by Radical Collaboration", sharing insights and contributing to the dialogue on creating resilient, climate-neutral cities through collaborative efforts.

DIGITALISING NEB: DIGINEB.EU'S BEST INSIGHTS AT SCEWC 2023

The first digiNEB.eu Annual Event at SCEWC 2023 marked a significant milestone in the journey of digital transformation within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) landscape. Hosted in the vibrant city of Barcelona, this hybrid event attracted 125 registrants, with 70 engaged participants actively contributing to the dialogues. It provided a comprehensive overview of the project's first-year achievements and future prospects

The event concluded with networking opportunities, allowing attendees to connect and discuss the insights shared, setting the stage for continued collaboration and innovation in the years to come.

Key sessions throughout the event included insightful presentations on the Digital Toolkit, designed to facilitate the implementation of NEB objectives, and the exploration of the elearning catalogue. Attendees also had the chance to learn from the experiences of early adopters of digital solutions for NEB.

A standout feature was the interactive session with the audience, engaging them directly in the conversation about digitalisation's role in a sustainable future. The panel discussion titled "The Digitalisation for a Sustainable Future - Shaping the New European Bauhaus" brought together experts like Deborah Navarra, Michael Mulquin, Cristina LaBianca, Odd Vinie, Eva Coscia, and Franco Vietti, to share their insights and visions.

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Learn more about

digiNEB.eu

digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus

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